

Revisiting Popular Myth in the Fictional World of Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's Novels

Satyendra Kumar Singh

Research Scholar, P. G. Dept. of English, V. K. S. U., Ara

Prof. K. K. Singh

P. G. Dept. of English, V. K. S. U., Ara

In modern Indian writing in English, there are a large number of women writers, especially women novelists who grab the opportunity to show their mastery over handling of such thematic perceptions which decode the role of women in typical traditional Indian society by making comparison and contrast with the past. In the novels of Githa Hariharan, Manju Kapoor, Jhumpa Lahiri, Kiran Desai, Chitra Bannerjee Divakaruni, Madhuri Mukherjee, Shashi Deshpande etc. we find the depiction of modern women in different contexts as opposed to the conventional woman as symbolized by Sita.

In the novels of Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni, we find the portrayal of Sita and Draupadi not as the traditional women suffering in the hands of male-dominated society, rather Chitra Bannerjee has decoded womanhood in analysing the character of Sita and Draupadi in her novels in terms of providing them real human status. In her novels *The Forest of Enchantment* and *The Palace of Illusions*, she analyses the characters of Sita and Draupadi by making them as real human beings and taking them free from the ambit of Goddesses. She beautifully narrates the human emotions and passions, hopes and aspirations, and failures and frustrations of these two women who have found their places in so many books in ancient as well as modern texts. Be it the representation of a woman from the traditional or the conventional perspective, or from the postcolonial perspectives, it seems that Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni gives a new

height altogether to her characters. This can be seen in *The Last Queen*—her recent novel. Unravelling the story of a modern women from a range of perspectives, Divakaruni carves out such an image of Rani Jindan Kaur, who despite being a daughter of a kennel keeper, i.e. a commoner, rises to the rank of being a queen and handles a range of courtly affairs not only during the lifetime of Maharaja Ranjit Singh, but also after his demise. Be it taking up arms against the British forces, or handing dexterously the internal affairs of the court, Rani emerges as a victorious woman character in the contemporary period. With the grass-root understanding of the everyday experiences and realities in life, Rani Jidan Kaur emerges as a perfect emblem of womanhood in the late eighteenth and early nineteenth century. Here, it would be apt to take a glance at such novels of Divakaruni, which decode Indian life in conflicting scenario.

Recipient of various prestigious awards and honours in recognition of her creative faculties and acumen, Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni is a reputed author, activist, poet and teacher of literature and life. Till date, she has authored nearly two dozen fiction books, which include novels as famous as *Mistress of Spices*, *Sister of My Heart*, *Oleander Girl*, *Before We Visit the Goddess*, and *Palace of Illusions*. Owner of citizenships of two nations, namely India and the United States, Chitra Banerjee was born in Calcutta (now Kolkata) in 1956. She completed her B. A. from the Calcutta University in 1976, M. A. from the Wright State University, Ohio in 1978; and the title of doctorate from the University of California, Berkeley in 1985. Initially she came to the United States to “pursue graduate work” (“Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni”). She served in the capacity of the Professor of creative writing at Diablo Valley College, California for a period of nearly three years, i.e. from 1987 to 1989. In the year 2015, she was included in the Economic Times List of 20 Most Influential Global Indian Women. To her credit, she also has the honour of judging several prestigious awards. This includes the PEN Faulkner Award and the National Book Award.

Apart from getting wide readership for her literary works, Divakaruni relishes the honour of having innumerable other feathers in her cap too. So far she has been published in nearly 100 magazines including those as prestigious as the *Atlantic Monthly*, the *Vogue*, the *Verve*, the *Elle*, the *O: The Oprah Magazine*, the *Best American Short Stories* and *The New Yorker*. Also, she has been included in three dozen anthologies. Her writings have been translated into more than two dozen languages across the world. This includes languages such as Dutch, Hebrew, Bengali, Hungarian, Turkish, Japanese and Hindi. Divakaruni is an independent, self-respectful (or self-respecting?) and ‘self-made’ woman too, at least in a certain sense. Striving for excellence in a foreign land, struggling to establish oneself as an author is indeed a challenge. During her initial stay full of a number of struggles in the United States, she would take up a whole range of jobs ranging from babysitting to selling merchandise in an Indian boutique to slicing bread in a bakery to washing instruments in a science lab” (“Divakaruni, Chitra Banerjee: Biography”).

Divakaruni has also written collections of short stories as well as poetry collections. Her short story collections include *Arranged Marriage: Stories* published from the Anchor Books, New York in the year 1995. Her poetry collections are *Dark Like the River* (1987), *The Reason for Nasturtiums* (1990) published by the Berkeley Poets Press, the *Black Candle: Poems about Women from India, Pakistan, and Bangladesh*, published by the Calyx Books in 1991, and *Leaving Yuba City: New and Selected Poems* published by the Anchor Books in 1997. Apart from the short story collections and the poetry collections, Chitra Banerjee has also edited two books, namely *Multitude: Cross-Cultural Readings for Writers* (1993) and *We, Too, Sing America: A Reader for Writers* (1998).

Most of her poems, short stories and the fictional writings revolve around the theme of women, their issues, female experiences, their struggle and expressions of their own. In order

to become adept in new ways of life, her characters seem to struggle really hard. In her writings, the love relationships between family members is also something complex. The conflict between the two cultural traditions is also a major concern in her writings. The two cultures here are the parent culture and the host culture, in other words the Indian culture and the American culture. Many of her short stories are considered supposedly autobiographical as they are set in the vicinity of the place she dwells in, i.e. California. The theme of migration, de-culturation, and enculturation of the migrant Indians is also a major concern in her writings. In other words, nearly all the writings of Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni are known for the portrayals of the immigrant Indian women's experiences in a foreign land. In a way, she seems to re-assess the role of Indian women abroad. In order to do so, she draws largely on her own experiences as well as those of other women.

Hitherto, Divakaruni has also edited two anthologies—*Multitude: Cross-Cultural Readings for Writers* (1997) and *We, Too, Sing America: A Reader for Writers* (1997). She has also authored a fair number of poetry collections, which include: *Dark Like the River* (1987), *The Reason for Nasturtiums* (1990), *Black Candle* (1991), and *Leaving Yuba City* (1997). These poetry collections include themes such as the representation of India and her culture, the experiences of Indians in America, and the condition of women and children in Indian society. In her case, art seems to percolate from one art form to another. For instance, to her, poetry is inspired by paintings, images and certain other visual sources. Pursuit for identity is yet another representative theme in her poems. This is visible in her first ever poetry collection—*Black Candle*. In this poetry collection she talks about the experiences of women from India, Pakistan and Bangladesh. Reviewing it, Nina Mehta in *Bloomsbury Review* observes, “how Divakaruni’s ‘straightforward narrative poems’ capture various levels of desperation and

despair, including women who are killed because their dowry was too small, who are driven into prostitution, or who end their lives” (qtd. in Singh “Introduction” xix).

Apart from poetry collections, she has also written collections of short stories. Her major short-story collection *Arranged Marriage* (1996) deals with the themes of conflict in the lives of women caught between two cultures, namely the culture of India on the one hand and that of America on the other. This collection of short-stories has been adapted into a play and staged in Canada and the USA. This short-story collection seems to be a fine example of intertextuality because according to some critics it has some thematic and ideational similarities with her poem under the same title “The Arranged Marriage”. Her collections of short stories are rich in terms of the themes they reflect upon. The themes of her work include divorce, abortion, racism, quest for identity, and economic inequality. Since her women characters are fraught with the harsh cultural realities of American culture, life-in-general is difficult for them. This is yet another theme in her stories. Precisely, the themes in her writings include various aspects and experiences of female identity in both India and America, the challenges of enculturation faced by the migrants, and the cultural conflicts of various other categories.

The novels of Divakaruni extend the same themes she once took in her poems and short stories. Her novels like *The Mistress of Spices* (1997) and *Sister of My Heart* (1999) portray the themes revolving around the immigrant experiences of Indians in the United States. How Indians, in particular women, translate the host culture; how multiculturalism in the context of Indian culture is a ‘norm’, how the institution of family works, how the trope of food serves as a medium to bind a whole range of sentiments and emotions in a family set up, how Bengali ethnicity thrives and sustains, how the immigrant characters undergo a predicament, a psychological-cultural shock and how they eventually ‘settle’ themselves in a foreign cultural set up are some of the major themes in the writings of Divakaruni. *The Mistress of Spices* is

considered as a fine blend of an experimentalist's ventures and poetic language. In Divakaruni's own words, "[The novel] collapses the divisions between the realistic world of twentieth century America and the timeless one of myth and magic in an attempt to create a modern fable" (Gearhart, "Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni Biography"). The *Mistress of Spices* also deals with themes of romance, the dynamics of supernatural immortal life and the modern life-style, love, struggle and the tension between opposing cultures etc. This novel is in the process of being made into an opera— a stage performance or a dramatized version of a narrative in one or more acts blended with music and dance, where required.

Yet another novel *Sister of My Heart* (1999) is considered the expansion of a short story titled "The Ultrasound " in her anthology *Arranged Marriage* (1996). Revolving around the lives of two cousins, namely Anju and Sudah, the novel discusses the themes of compassion, companionship, and affection between the two. Commonalities in their experiences, the novel narrates the story of affinity between the duo, who grew up in the same house in Calcutta. This affinity leads them to believe that they are the sisters of the heart—two individuals yet associated with one another by heart, by emotions, by sentiments at the plane of ethereality. However, "their unique relationship is tasted, and the women struggle in the face of doubt and suspicion" (Gearhart *Contemporary Novelists* 256). The duo separate in the course of time and story, however, the similarities in their lives keep them tied, or give a semblance of union by heart despite being away from one another physically and geographically.

The level of ease (or difficulty) of life in both India and America is one of the substantial concerns in her writings. In particular, how women characters face adverse circumstances, and eventually, how glorious and successful they emerge in the face of difficulties, is yet another key concern in her writings. Her stories collected in *Arranged Marriage* reflect on such issues quite emphatically. The dialectics of existence in the lives of characters, who are swinging

between Indian cultural expectations and the American cultural realities is a considerable issue in her writings as well.

A very significant aspect of Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's writings is that, in a certain sense, she seems to raise the voice of the female. This can be seen in her latest literary writing *Independence* also. Though a lot has been written and documented both historically and literarily on the theme of partition, still it seems that the voices of the female population have not been explored adequately. It seems that they are underexplored. In one of the online articles written by Udbhav Seth entitled "When We Silence the Multiplicity of Voices, What are We Left with: Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni", he showcases how the voices of women have been absent from the literary-historical writings. Not only that, she also expresses her concern over the necessity of inclusivity in the contemporary society in which more and more intolerance against the 'refugees' or immigrants has been taken seriously. She casts light on issues such as the seriousness that needs to be attached to inclusivity.

Chitra Banerjee seems to highlight woman in different perspectives. In her recent novel she would like to put her woman characters in the context of historical perspectives, particularly in the course of partition how women suffered in multiple ways in the hands of men as well as imposed circumstances. They were the victims of both time and space, if unfortunately they found themselves in opposite camp, their condition was quite out of imagination as we find in different partition novels based on the real happenings. The partition of Indian and Pakistan brought multiple shocks to women, particularly because of the traditional and conventional state of contemporary society, which did not allow them "homecoming". In this sense, her recent writing is the real replica of changing womanhood in the wake of modern civilization which allows women to rethink and reconstruct human values suitable for their survival. This novel is the continuation of her three early novels *The Forest of Enchantment*, *The Palace of*

Illusion and The Last Queen in terms of delineating women in entirely different perspective as opposed to the traditional and conventional modes of understanding. The central protagonist of this novel does not stand in the line of the submission of Sita and Draupadi, rather she is more vibrant for her integrity and status as a “human being.” Even though the novel ends on a sad and melancholic note because of the gloomy atmosphere but story is quite inspiring in nature in terms of projecting the heroic struggle of the sisters for their survival.

Divakaruni has invested time in research in the partition narrative because this novel studies the features of independence. She ironically studies the motive of Mahatma Gandhi and Jawaharlal Nehru who were in favour of Indian independence around 1947, but whether they were in favour of the independence of “united India” or “divided India” it is not documented. The writer has narrated the gloomy atmosphere that prevailed around 1946-1947 but she is not clear about her own motive either to support independence of “united India” or “divided India”. The independence was the result of long struggle of almost two hundred years in which more than million people sacrificed their life, but the achievement at the last was not satisfying because Hindu majority in large were not in position to accept the independence of divided India as it was considered as the political failure of the top contemporary leaders, especially Mahatma Gandhi and Jawaharlal Nehru. This reality also been suggested by Divakaruni in straightforward manner. Like the dream of three sisters—Deepa, Priya and Jamini—the dream of millions of Bengalis was shattered by the partition of Bengal into two parts in 1947. For the writer, violence is not the issue, the real issue lies in emotional and sentimental breakdown of the sisters who found themselves “nowhere” after partition. The same people became violent at once because of displacement and it was a great threat to humanity. Divakaruni has revisited the partition theme in this novel and succeeded in narrating the most poignant tale of three sisters victimised by the partition of Bengal. This novel has multiple layers of narrative

unfolding and decoding human behaviour at different level from the woman's perspective. Perhaps this novel is quite unique from the other partition novels highlighting the horrifying and terrible effect of partition on the psyche of women.

Literary tradition has been replete with telling of one particular narrative from multiple angles. Telling of a narrative by a male author has to essentially differ from the telling by a female author. This has been a contested territory indeed for various reasons. One prominent reason is that what a woman undergoes cannot be completely assimilated and perceived by the psyche of male author. The intensity of a trauma, agony or another female experience has to essentially differ when narrativised by a male author. This also happens in the case of Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni when she candidly tells "It is crucial for me to allow a woman to tell her own story" (Agrawal, *The Indian Express*). Divakaruni is of the view that only women can tell the story of a woman because she alone understands the agony and trauma suffered by a woman. She also emphasises that woman is still in the stigma of marginalization because of so many things altogether and it is extremely difficult for a woman to break the cobweb of the politics played for their emancipation. Nowadays, a large number of programmes run by the government and NGOs for stabilizing women and consolidating their position in terms of social and economic upliftment, but unless and until these movements are supported by human motif, the desired results could not be achieved. Women are still in minority in spite of the fact they are almost half of the entire population of the world. She finds difficult to compare herself with male writers in terms of creativity. In her two novels *The Forest of Enchantment* based on the narrative of *the Ramayana*, and *The Palace of Illusions* based on the famous stories of the Mahabharata, Divakaruni succeeds in telling the stories of Sita and Draupadi in different perspectives. For her Sita and Draupadi and not mere incarnations, but they are also made up of human flesh and blood like ordinary human beings they think and feel. These novels have

been written from the female perspectives as perceived by Sita and Draupadi. For Sita apart from her wifely submission and devotion, her own character has emerged uniquely in this novel and she is not mere foil to Ram. For her sacrifice alone does not matter, rather she would like to maintain her individuality and that is quite apparent in her relationship with her sister-in-law Shanta who was the sister of her husband Ram. In order to maintain the individuality of Sita, Divakaruni has presented the relationship between Sita and Shanta in detail just in order to provide human status to the character of Sita. Like a typical relationship between *nanad* and *bhaujai*, the relationship between Sita and Shanta was not peaceful and full of harmony. This sense of narrative is quite modern in delineation because it decodes the relationship between *nanad* and *bhaujai* in modern period. Sita finds uncomfortable in the company of Shanta and also her mother-in-law Kaikeyi. Divakaruni highlights such relationships with a sense of modern perspective and also in order to provide a sense of realistic approach towards highlighting such problems occurred in everyday life.

Similarly, in her novel *The Palace of Illusions*, the case of Draupadi is quite pathetic in nature. Arjun had owned her in swayamvar organized for the marriage of Draupadi by her father Drupad. When Arjun took her to his own house in the forest, unfortunately without seeing her, Kunti ordered Arjun to ‘distribute’ her among his brothers. Here, it is quite noteworthy that Draupadi has been taken as an object. But the tradition did not allow Kunti to rectify her order and being the loyal son, Arjun along with his brother married Draupadi. Thus, she became the wife of five husbands and this was quite abusive for her because people like Duryodhan, Karna, and Dushashan were always busy in making comments regarding this status of hers. Draupadi did not oppose the words of her mother-in-law and Arjun and easily bowed down before the decision of her mother-in-law. This narrative is quite suggestive in showing a blow on the part of a woman as an entity in general.

Chitra Banerjee differs from other contemporary woman novelists in various ways, especially in terms of the presentation of women as a human being in the context of a male-dominated society which does not allow required freedom and liberty to women for free grooming and blooming. Manju Kapoor and Jhumpa Lahiri are two other novelists writing their works in the same line but they have different approaches towards the presentation of women in modern context. Manju Kapoor limits herself to a little bit of ivory in decoding human relationships in her novels. Her novels *Difficult Daughters*, *Home*, *The Immigrant*, *Brothers* etc. throw light on various aspects of man-woman relationship in the wake of modernity. The brilliance of the novelist lies in the fact that she is able to establish parallelism between her esoteric and private presentation linked with some national issues. For instance in her novel *Difficult Daughters* she tells the story of a mother and her daughters finding themselves in difficult phase of their life.

Works Cited:-

1. "Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni: Ancora Imparo." *Chitradivakaruni.com*, 20 September, 2022, <https://www.chitradivakaruni.com/books/leaving-yuba-city>.
2. "Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni." *Poetry Foundation*, 18 September, 2022, <https://www.poetryfoundation.org/poets/chitra-banerjee-divakaruni>.
3. Divakaruni, Chitra Banerjee: Biography." *scholarblogs.emory.edu*, <https://scholarblogs.emory.edu/postcolonialstudies/2014/06/10/divakaruni-chitra-banerjee/>
4. Gearhart, Stephanie. "Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni Biography." *biography.jrank.org*.
Open web

5. Source, https://biography.jrank.org/pages/_4269/Divakaruni-Chitra-Banerjee.html, Web, 18 September, 2022.
6. “Independence: A Novel.” *Wikipedia.org*. *En.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Independence_(novel)*. Accessed on 22 November, 2023.
7. Singh, Amritjit et al. eds. “Introduction.” *Critical Perspectives on Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni: Feminism and Diaspora*, Lexington Books, 2022, pp. Xv-xxxv.
8. Schlager, Neil and Josh Lauer. eds. *Contemporary Novelists: Seventh Edition*. St. James Press, 2001.
9. Narayan, R. K. *The Painter of Signs*, Mysore, Indian Thoughts Publications, 1999
10. Narayan, R. K. *The Dark Room*, Mysore, Indian Thoughts Publications, 1999
11. Banerjee, Chitra. *The Forest of Enchantments* HarperCollins, India, 2021
12. Banerjee, Chitra. *The Palace of Illusions* Penguin Random House, India, 2018
13. Banerjee, Chitra. *The Last Queen*, HarperCollins, India, 2021
14. Kapur, Manju. *A Married Woman*, Penguin Random House, India, 2018
15. Kapur, Manju. *Difficult Daughters* Penguin Random House, India, 2018
16. Kapur, Manju. *Custody* Penguin Random House, India, 2018
17. Kapur, Manju. *Brothers* Penguin Random House, India, 2018
18. Anand, M. R. *Untouchable*, OUP, India, 2011
19. Anand, M. R. *Coolie*, OUP, India, 2001